

Improving the Performance of Higher Education Organizations in Timor - LESTE

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Abstract

Higher education as a center for the discovery of new knowledge that can answer various problems faced by society in this era of globalization. The pulse of scientific development is concentrated in study programs and good study programs come from the intellectual abilities of the program head in compiling the curriculum and recruiting competent lecturers to teach courses. A good study program head must have a transformational leadership style to support lecturers to carry out their teaching duties well and conduct research to discover new knowledge. The theoretical basis in this article is Resource-based theory. This study provides practical knowledge for higher education in Timor-Leste in terms of organizational learning, thus every leader and lecturer continues to learn through the development of a system of thinking about past events as a guideline to guide lecturers to learn better in building a more rational lecture system, thus producing quality graduates to contribute to the development of education in Timor-Leste. This study provides practical knowledge for higher education in Timor-Leste, especially organizational capabilities, thus leaders can manage human resources and material resources in higher education to improve organizational performance. By using existing internet technology to improve the education system in Timor-Leste, it can thus improve organizational performance

Keywords: Transformational leadership, Organizational learning, Organizational capabilities and performance

Introduction

A college is a place provided by an organization, either government or private, to accommodate the nation's sons and daughters who have completed their education in high school (SMA) to continue their education at a higher level, known as a college. The philosophy of college is to conduct research to find new knowledge that is useful for society, not like high schools which focus only on learning knowledge. To find new knowledge in college requires a visionary leader. Leadership is a process by which someone can influence others and groups to achieve organizational goals. To achieve organizational goals, a leader needs good knowledge and skills in order to build the organization systematically through predetermined stages. Gusmao, et. al. (2018:124), the role of leadership is very

strategic and significant for the organization and determines the achievement of the vision, mission and goals of the organization. Leadership is always related to the ability and skills to be able to work together with others to achieve the ideals of the organization. The achievements of the Higher Education Foundation in Timor-Leste must be able to contribute to the development goals of the country of Timor-Leste. As stipulated in the Constitution of the Democratic Republic of Timor Leste, (2002:10), article 6, namely the State guarantees a decent life for citizens in a sustainable manner. The goals of this country are in line with the world development guidelines known as the Millennium Development Goals, which are a reference for all member countries of the United Nations.

Development is a process that involves many aspects, one of which is the aspect of education, because education is a way to shape the mentality and transfer knowledge to the community so that it is useful for themselves and others. Amaral, et. al. (2014:11), education has an important role in producing reliable human resources. Service providers, education has an obligation to create quality humans through an effective education process. Effective education is a way of working that is carried out appropriately according to the time plan and goals that the organization has determined. Ruddock (1997:279), a job is done effectively if the job gives good results to the organization. Effective education is related to efficiency, namely using limited human and material resources but producing satisfactory results for the organization (Sharma & Adeoye, 2024).

To create an independent and prosperous society requires a transformational leader who is visionary and able to socialize the vision and mission of the organization to subordinates so that all academicians can know and implement it. Universities through faculties can open new study programs led by the head of the study program can compile a curriculum according to market needs which are outlined in the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP). Mutahar, et. al. (2015:5), transformational leadership is a style that can increase awareness and collective interests among members of the organization and help them achieve common goals. Leaders must bring change to the organization to achieve organizational goals, in the leadership process one of the characteristics that a leader must have is being required to behave well so that their presence can be accepted by members of the organization. Character is a mental attitude that a person has to relate to others. Simanjuntak, et. al. (2020:224), the characteristics of individual employees with good character will make it easier for the employee to do his job, and vice versa, employees with bad characteristics will hinder an organization from operating and developing. Gusmao, et. al. (2015), good organizational behavior or often referred to as organizational citizenship behavior is important to achieve because it will provide a positive contribution to the quality of work and organizational performance.

Higher education institutions in Timor-Leste continue to learn in facing the global situation that continues to change and innovate in accordance with market demands in people's lives. Organizational learning is one way to improve quality academic institutions through individuals who continue to learn. Gusmao, et. al. (2018), said

that organizational learning is an organizational skill to create, obtain, interpret, transfer, share knowledge, with the aim of modifying behavior to describe knowledge with new insights. Akhtar et al. (2011), organizational learning has gained a significant place over the past few decades. Learning is defined as a way to understand others and yourself. Organizational learning can be likened to a mirror to see the shortcomings that exist in us so that they can be improved for the better. Ruddock (1997), Education is a process of teaching knowledge and skills that are given to others, which in the end can change the lives of others for the better. This means that education is a vitamin that creates good nutrition for human common sense to think critically in analyzing problems that exist in higher education organizations. In fact, higher education is the center of human common sense.

Leaders of universities in Timor-Leste do not yet have a good leadership style in universities. The results of research by Amaral, et. al. (2014), show that private universities in Timor-Leste have experienced a decline in the number of registered students, this occurs because some universities in each faculty do not yet have Standard Operating Procedures or SOPs, and some of their lecturers have not been able to compile teaching syllabi. This happens because some heads of study programs do not yet have the ability to prepare plans to increase the capacity of lecturers in writing syllabi, lack of research plans and journal publications. Many study programs at universities in Timor-Leste, especially at the undergraduate level, have very low interest in this case the number of students is below 15 people. This phenomenon occurs in both state and private universities and this problem occurs every year. Data from the national accreditation body (2023). There are several study programs that have been opened for almost 10 years but have not been accredited by the national accreditation body because they do not meet the basic criteria. These phenomena are related to the leadership capabilities that exist in universities in Timor-Leste, which do not think strategically in anticipating current and future conditions. Thus, it requires a transformational leader, so the author emphasizes the existence of transformational leadership. Organizational learning is related to the existence of study programs that have not been accredited for 10 years, meaning that there is less learning from other organizations to build a good learning plan. Organizational capabilities are associated with university leaders who do not prepare good plans in utilizing existing human resources both from outside Timor-Leste and those in Timor-Leste in strengthening study programs in Timor-Leste, weaknesses affect the performance of universities in Timor-Leste, for example the number of students who register for college in the early years is not balanced with the number of graduates or graduations. Phenomena in universities in Timor-Leste can affect economic growth in Timor-Leste because universities are the center of science and technology in a country. The World Bank report shows that unemployment in Timor-Leste reached 52.9% living on a daily income of US\$ 1,940 (Nahak & Ellitan, 2023:5).

Problem Formulation

Based on the description of the background reinforced by the conceptual model related to the influence of transformational leadership on organizational performance, through Organizational Learning, and capability as an intervening variable in universities in Timor-Leste, it is clear that transformational leadership can affect organizational performance. The presence of organizational learning and capability is believed to be able to strengthen the influence of transformational leadership on organizational performance. Based on this argument, the formulation of the problem of this study is whether the aspects of organizational learning and leader capability are able to strengthen the influence of transformational leadership on organizational performance. Therefore, the research questions are as follows:

Literature Review

Leadership and Capabilities

Sriwidadi (2014:278), in his research results showed that transformational leadership has a significant effect on organizational capabilities. While Widiatmaka, et. al. (2023), dynamic managerial capabilities are directly related to organizational performance, and dynamic managerial capabilities are able to make strategic change decisions to improve organizational innovation capabilities which in turn improve organizational performance. The main thing in dynamic capabilities is fast cooperation, finding new market places, so that the company is in a stable state. The findings in public educational organizations at shipping colleges in Indonesia show that managerial capabilities have a significant relationship with organizational performance. So transformational managerial leadership in building an organization can influence organizational performance to improve organizational performance.

Transformational Leadership and Organizational Performance

According to Putro et al. (2017), a leader must apply a leadership style to manage subordinates, because leaders will greatly influence success in achieving organizational goals. Correa et. al. (2005:355), the results of the study showed that there was a significant relationship between transformational leadership and organizational performance because transformational leadership has a positive impact on members to work more effectively and innovatively through program implementation, thus achieving organizational goals.

Ulum, et. al. (2020:299), showed that leadership style can improve teacher or lecturer performance. A school leader must have a clear and realistic strategy. Having concern, and being able to encourage members, maintain team cohesion, and appreciate differences of opinion can improve teacher performance. Previous research from Siregar (2018) stated that the principal's leadership affects teacher performance. It can be said that transformational leadership with strategies that support and facilitate teachers can improve organizational performance.

Organizational Learning and Capabilities

Organizational Learning and Capabilities are two components that synergize with each other because capabilities are abilities that are united in a person before joining an organization. For example, everyone in the family has been taught how to survive with the resources around them. In everyday life, individuals begin to interact with each other, in that interaction people learn new things from one family to another which is often referred to as informal education. Chen & Zheng (2022:5), stated that organizational learning is behavior and learning processes that bring and improve the long-term adaptability of a company. Learning is the key to changing and restructuring the operational capabilities of the human resource service industry. Chen Zhen (2022) in his research results found that organizational learning has a positive impact on capabilities. Antunes, et. al. (2020) in Chen (2022), observers of organizational learning focus more on the acquisition of organizational knowledge and the continuous transformation of learning outcomes, which are reflected in the process of finding knowledge, using knowledge and creating knowledge. So it can be interpreted that organizational learning can improve the capabilities of individuals working in the company and contribute to organizational capabilities.

Organizational Learning and Organizational Performance

Organizational learning is an act of learning carried out by each individual or group in an organization because they have the same goal. In this discussion, an academic learning process carried out by academics at Timor-Leste universities in serving the academic community of women and men who study at universities with different expertise according to the study program being studied. Learning involves both social life and educational organizations. Learning itself is used by individuals to improve their lives and for organizations to improve work, in this case the organization is developing both in terms of the number of enthusiasts becoming large and more financial income, then the organization achieves its goals. Ouma & Kombo (2016), stated that organizational learning is a collective effort, today the dynamics of the business environment require that everyone must continue to learn to face tight market competition.

The results of Ouma & Kombo's research (2016), showed a significant relationship between organizational learning and organizational performance. Kalmuk & Acar (2015). The orientation of organizational learning directly affects company performance. Meanwhile, Aragon & Morales (2022), the results of the literature review found that organizational learning affects organizational performance in companies. This happens because organizations continue to learn. This means that it can be interpreted that organizational learning is a continuous learning process that must be carried out by individuals without stopping, like breathing in humans for 24 hours continuously requiring air. So organizational learning is like human life which always needs air for human breathing. If individuals stop learning, the organization will not develop, meaning that universities must continue to learn to understand the conditions within the university or vice versa.

Transformational Leadership and Organizational Learning

Transformational leadership is a style that can influence all forms of organizational activities, because activities are driven by individuals who continue to learn to improve organizational performance. According to Noruzy (2013:12), the results of the study showed that transformational leadership has a significant relationship with organizational learning. Many studies have stated that there is a significant relationship between transformational leadership and organizational learning. Organizational learning is a collective part including: interpretation, information, organizational memory, so organizational learning is an important basis for the sustainability of the organization, because only by learning and learning can all the problems around it be applied and learning is the foundation for an ordinary employee to the leadership ladder. In short, learning is the initial capital to become a leader. Capability mediates the relationship between leadership and organizational performance, capability can mediate leadership and organizational performance.

Diantoro et al. (2023), states that entrepreneurial leadership facilitates the innovation process and contributes to the adaptation of organizations and dynamic business environments. This study shows that there is a relationship between entrepreneurial leadership and achieving higher company performance. Leadership is a successful strategic way to achieve organizational goals. Thanle et al. (2021: 5), states that the ability to change to improve organizational performance is the goal of all organizations to develop sustainably. The results of the study showed that there was a significant and positive influence between transformational leadership and capability, and there was a significant relationship between leadership and organizational performance. Gumanti (2009:2), the company has the advantage of mastering information than external parties who have interests with the company. This shows that the role of capability in mediating leadership to improve organizational performance is an innovative and progressive effort that requires team cohesion in the organization so that all resources can be united in facing competition with external parties.

The Relationship between Capability, Organizational Learning and Organizational Performance

Adiputra & Mandala (2017), change capability in an organization is an effort that must continue to be encouraged in order to achieve organizational goals, in the results of their research shows that there is a positive relationship between capability and organizational performance. Organizational capability is an important element for creating organizational performance because a company can achieve its goals if the organization's people have good abilities in working both internally and externally. Organizational learning is a continuous learning process in various organizations today, because only continuing to learn can make a major contribution to the organization, all members of the organization must continue to reflect on themselves on what has been done to have a positive impact on supporting the organization to continue to grow or hinder organizational performance. That is

not a problem in organizational ability, but what is more important is what management must do so that the organization, or take wisdom from a dynamic journey in learning.

Menon et al. (1999), in Berliana & Arsanti (2018: 149-161), stated that capability is the process of applying the abilities, knowledge, and experience possessed by human resources to implement predetermined strategies and can provide value to an organization. Furthermore, Menon said that good work capability will produce good performance, the higher the capability a person has, the higher the performance of the organization. The results of the study showed a positive and significant relationship that capability can mediate organizational performance and have a positive effect. Yang et al. (2023: 1016), the existence of a significant link or relationship between leadership and capability can improve organizational performance in Indonesia. The results of the study on a number of private higher education institutions in Indonesia. Thanh Le, et al. (2021: 11747), the results of the study showed a positive and significant relationship between organizational capability and leadership. Organizational capability significantly mediates transformational leadership in practice and organizational performance, especially increasing good financial performance in companies

Capability, Organizational Learning and Organizational Performance

Rauch et al. (2009), emphasizes the role of capability in shaping an organization's ability to innovate and adapt to technological advances, running well requires leadership in improving organizational performance. Meanwhile, Kunartinah & Sukoco (2010: 74), the results of empirical research show that the existence of organizational capability has a positive influence on organizational performance, capability has a positive influence on organizational learning and organizational learning has an effect on organizational performance.

According to Rehman, et. al. (2019), organizational learning functions to strengthen organizational capabilities and the final result is to improve organizational performance. The results of research from Herman (2018) show that there are some that show a significant relationship between organizational capabilities and performance, but some have weak results. Junquera, et. al. (2016), in Rehman, et. al. (2019), the results show that there are some that are positive but some are negative. Hidayat et al. (2022:23), shows that knowledge management capabilities have a positive influence on organizational learning and can improve organizational performance. Tseng & Lee, (2014), show that knowledge management capabilities have a positive influence on organizational performance. Gomes et al. (2021), states that innovative organizational learning capabilities can affect organizational performance.

Discussion: Improving The Performance of Timor Leste Higher Education Improving Performance through Transformational Leadership and Organizational Capabilities

A successful organization needs a leader who has high intellectual abilities to stimulate subordinates to work according to procedures in order to achieve organizational goals. The results of this study support the theory of transformational leadership proposed by Bass & Avolio (1993), with 4 indicators including: idealist influence, inspiration motivation, intellectual stimulation and individual consideration. Empirically, the results of the study support the results of the study of Sriwidadi (2014:278), in the results of his research showed that transformational leadership has a significant effect on organizational capabilities. Thus, the higher the head of study programs at universities in Timor-Leste gives trust to lecturers to conduct more research and publish it, it will have a positive and significant influence on students to learn new knowledge taught by lecturers, in order to respond to real conditions in the field, because basically universities are different from elementary schools to high schools which only focus on learning concepts, while the philosophy of higher education is not to learn concepts but to find new concepts and new knowledge through research whose basis is guided by rational and methodological logic. Such as observing phenomena, formulating problems, building hypotheses that are strengthened by theory and conducting research, and the research is published so that it will be read by many people and will help others to change their lives for the better.

Improving Performance through Organizational Learning and Organizational Capabilities

A good organization is an organization that continues to learn from past experiences both from within the organization itself and from the experiences of other organizations, to improve the organization for the better. The results of this study support the theory of organizational learning proposed by Marquart (1996), which consists of 5 indicators, including: development of thinking systems, mental models, personal skills, teamwork and shared vision. Of the five indicators, the highest respondent frequency is in the personal ability indicator with a score of 87% which is supported by 4 question items, the basic question is that the head of the study program always gives lecturers the opportunity to make decisions based on beliefs, choose good teaching methods, be open to students by accepting input from students to improve the learning process. good so that it can achieve organizational goals. Personal ability is the basic foundation in an organization, because the strength of the organization is the accumulation of strength from individuals who continue to learn tirelessly, the process of continuing to learn is like a wasp or bee looking for sweet nectar from various flowers that come from plants which are then managed naturally to produce sweet and delicious honey water for human consumption to be healthy. In relation to the teaching and learning process, lecturers are led by the head of the study program to learn to read various sources of knowledge from anywhere, which are poured into a module which is then planned

systematically in a teaching plan to teach students. Meanwhile, in the implementation in the field, the results of this study are related to the results of previous research conducted by Chen (2022), in the results of his research found that organizational learning has a positive impact on capabilities. Antunes, et. al. (2020), in (Chen 2022) said that observers of organizational learning focus more on the acquisition of organizational knowledge and the continuous transformation of learning outcomes, which are reflected in the process of finding knowledge, using and creating knowledge. So it can be interpreted that organizational learning can improve the capabilities of individuals working in companies and contribute to organizational capabilities. If lecturers in universities continue to learn, universities in Timor-Leste will be more advanced in the future.

Organizations everywhere always need resources, both human resources and other materials, to drive organizational goals. The results of this study support the findings of previous studies put forward by Mulyono (2013:128), stating that company capabilities in the Resource-based view theory are important internal factors in managing resources that the company already has so that the company is able to achieve competitive advantage or competitiveness. Company capabilities are also assessed as the ability to carry out coordinated tasks or activities in order to achieve company goals. the human resource management factor is very important, such as the statement of the item from the human resource management indicator, that the head of the study program always assigns lecturers based on educational background and work experience.

The results of this study support the results of previous studies, namely Adiputra & Mandala (2017), the capability of change in an organization is an effort that must continue to be encouraged in order to achieve organizational goals, in the results of their research showed that there is a positive relationship between capability and organizational performance. Because the research supports the results of previous studies, the increasing number of study program heads in managing human resources effectively and efficiently will create quality graduates, thus being able to overcome economic conditions and other social problems better in the future.

The presence of a leader in an organization is very important for making plans, implementing plans, supervising and evaluating, thus achieving organizational goals. The results of this study are related to the theory developed by Effiyanti, et. al. (2021:584), defining leadership as a skill to influence groups to achieve a vision or goal. Transformational leadership is described as a process characterized by interaction between leaders and followers to promote each other to a higher level of morality with motivation to achieve organizational goals. Empirically, the results of the analysis found that leadership has a positive but insignificant influence on organizational performance. The results of the study are in contrast to the results of previous studies presented by Correa et. al. (2005:355), saying that there is a significant relationship between transformational leadership and organizational performance because transformational leadership has a positive impact on members to work more effectively and innovatively through program implementation, thus

achieving organizational goals. This can happen because the cultural factor of implementing leadership styles in each university has not maximized the implementation of transformational leadership styles based on the indicator measurements determined by Bass (1993). There are some heads of study programs who have not implemented transformational leadership styles optimally, this can be measured by the frequency of respondents who are different for each indicator so that they are only positive but not significant. This can be seen in the first indicator of the influence of ideas with the main question, namely that "the head of the study program is optimistic and believes that each lecturer will carry out tasks such as having a syllabus, learning plans, all with good methods so that they can achieve the objectives of each assigned course. But the reality may be that some study programs do not believe that each lecturer can carry out their duties by teaching well in this case the quality of teaching because each lecturer has different abilities and the reality is that many lecturers do not have a teaching syllabus. This can be measured by the frequency of answers from respondents, especially the first indicator with the first question only getting a score of strongly agreeing with only 26% of nine respondents. In short, it can be said that each head of the study program has implemented a transformational leadership style but in practice it has not been fully implemented by each lecturer, perhaps because the reading culture is still low and also the skills in writing are still low. So in the future there needs to be more training in writing skills.

The Role of Organizational Capability and Transformational Leadership Integration in Organizational Performance Improvement

The results of this study are related to the Resource-based theory developed by Penroce (1959), namely about growth which is basically based on the management of human resources and other resources to achieve organizational goals. This study uses two indicators, namely human resource management and the use of technology to achieve study program goals. The results show that capability can mediate transformational leadership has a positive effect on organizational performance but is not significant. This means that the results of this study support previous research, namely the results of research from Kunartinah & Sukoco (2010: 74), the results of empirical research show that the existence of organizational capability has a positive effect on organizational performance. But the results of this study do not fully support the results of research from Menon et al. (1999), because the findings of Menon et al. (1999) there is a positive and significant relationship between capability can mediate organizational performance positive and significant results. The results are only positive but not significant, there is some truth because of the two indicators used in the study got different scores where human resource management scored higher and the technology utilization indicator. The utilization of technology supported by basic questions, namely the utilization of technology such as the availability of laboratories for practice for students in universities is still very low, meaning that not all universities have complete laboratories for students to practice.

The Role of Organizational Capability and Organizational Learning Integration in Organizational Performance Improvement

The results of the study found a positive and significant relationship between organizational capability in mediating organizational learning in improving organizational performance. This means that the results of this study support previous research conducted by Adiputra & Mandala (2017), Change capability in an organization is an effort that must continue to be encouraged in order to achieve organizational goals, in the results of their research showed that there is a relationship between capability and organizational performance. Organizational capability is an important element for creating organizational performance because a company can achieve its goals if the organization's people have good abilities in working both internally and externally. Organizational learning is a continuous learning process in various organizations today, because only continuing to learn can make a major contribution to the organization, all members of the organization must continue to reflect on themselves on what has been done has a positive impact on supporting the organization to continue to develop or hinder organizational performance.

Conclusion

The results of this study are expected to contribute to the management of Higher Education in Timor Leste in several aspects according to the variables of this study, namely: This study provides practical knowledge for Higher Education in Timor-Leste, namely the importance of the role of transformational leadership in inspiring lecturers, and intellectual stimulation in motivating lecturers to work to improve the performance of Higher Education organizations, through critical thoughts to provide quality input in building a good educational curriculum. This paper provides practical knowledge for higher education in Timor-Leste in terms of organizational learning, thus every leader and lecturer continues to learn through the development of a system of thinking about past events as a guideline to guide lecturers to learn better in building a more rational lecture system, thus producing quality graduates to contribute to the development of education in Timor-Leste. This study provides practical knowledge for higher education in Timor-Leste, especially organizational capabilities, thus leaders can manage human resources and material resources in higher education to improve organizational performance. By using existing internet technology to improve the education system in Timor-Leste, it can thus improve organizational performance

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